

HISTORIOGRAPHY OF THE HISTORY OF THE RAILWAY SYSTEM IN THE SURKHAN OASIS

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Abstract: In this article The works of local historians, which reflected in our information about the strategic importance of the eastern regions of the Bukhara Emirate, were analyzed in historical consistency.

Key words: Czarist Russia, England, East Bukhara, railway, local sources, Muhammad Vafoyi Karminaghi.

Аннотация: В данной статье в исторической непротиворечивости проанализированы труды краеведов, отразившие в наших сведениях о стратегическом значении восточных районов Бухарского эмирата.

Ключевые слова: Царская Россия, Англия, Восточная Бухара, железная дорога, местные источники, Мухаммад Вафойи Карминаги.

In the second half of the 19th century, the integration of Central Asia into Russia was completed. The tsarist government took all measures to strengthen its power in the newly conquered country and to exploit its natural resources. Among the many activities carried out by Tsarism, the construction of railways in the region took an important place. Their need was related to political, military-strategic and economic reasons. The tsarist government sought to strengthen its position over the peoples of Turkestan, Bukhara Emirate and Khiva Khanate. By the middle of the 19th century, the rivalry between the Russian Empire and England also intensified [1].

The annexation of the Kokand Khanate, the subjugation of Bukhara and Khiva led to an even more intense Anglo-Russian conflict. In 1873, as a result of long negotiations between Russia and England, an agreement was reached to limit the spheres of influence in these regions of Asia. According to the agreement, the land up to the Amudarya and the territories of Turkestan were transferred to Russia`s sphere of influence, and Afghanistan (with the condition of maintaining its independence) to England`s sphere of influence [2].

But even after the conclusion of the treaty, the Anglo-Russian rivalry in Central Asia did not stop. Both sides sought to expand their spheres of influence. In 1878-1880, the second Anglo-Afghan war began in Afghanistan, as a result of which the country became completely dependent on England. Naturally, under such conditions, Anglo-Russian confrontations became more intense.

The tsarist government was forced to take urgent measures to secure its position in Turkestan. For this, first of all, a railway connecting the central

regions of Russia with the remote region was needed. It should be noted that three military districts (Turkestan, Orenburg and Siberia) were mobilized in case of any complications in foreign policy on the borders of Turkestan. At the same time, not only a large amount of money was spent on the transfer of troops and ammunition, but also a long time (usually up to 10 months). The Khiva campaign of 1873 showed the tsarist military command that the old method of moving troops would cause irreparable losses to the Russian army [3].

In the 70s of the 19th century, the need to build a railway in Central Asia was primarily connected with political and military-strategic issues. At the same time, the railway in the occupied region was also necessary for economic reasons. Central Asia has long been of interest to the Russian Empire as an important market and source of raw materials. After annexing this vast territory to Russia, the tsarist government and Russian capitalists were interested in adapting the economy of the new region to the needs of the developing Russian industry [4]. At this point, it should be noted that Eastern Bukhara, which is considered a border region with Afghanistan, and located in a favorable geographical environment, rich in natural resources, was of great importance. The main goal of the Russian Empire was to master the natural resources in this area.

The process of elucidating information about the strategic importance of the eastern regions of the Bukhara Emirate began in the second half of the 19th century, and such research can be found in the information and memories of the officials and soldiers of the Russian Empire. In addition, scientific research was conducted in the Soviet period and in the years of independence. Scientific research and literature on the topic were studied in the following groups:

1. Literature published during the colonial period of the Russian Empire.
2. Scientific research and literature published during the Soviet rule.
3. Scientific research and published literature during the years of Uzbekistan's independence.

In the second half of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, the collection of works and information belonging to the first period, created by direct witnesses and participants of the historical events of this period, are now rare written sources in terms of their value and importance. Considering that they are recognized as written sources by the scientific community, we decided to include them as primary sources and used them as sources. Therefore, we found it necessary to dwell in detail on these works in the source base of our work.

The works written by local historians are of particular importance in the study of the history of Eastern Bukhara provinces, which are part of the Bukhara Emirate. Sources related to the history of the Eastern Bukhara province during the period we are researching can be divided into the following groups:

- works of local historians;
- archival materials;
- information, memoirs and reports written by Russian officials, military, tourists, geographers.

In writing this research work, local written sources, the colonial period of the Bukhara Emirate and the Russian Empire are illuminated and organized historical research on the topic created during that period. The authors of these works directly saw that period with their own eyes and are a collection of works and information created by the participants of the events. Today, in terms of their value and importance, these works are at the level of rare manuscript sources and researches .

In general, from local written sources Muhammad Vafoyi Karminaghi's "Khan's gift" or "Tarihi Rahimkhani" (History of Muhammad Rahim Khan)[5], Mulla Ibodullah and Mulla Muhammad Sharif's "Tarihi Amir Haidar" (History of Amir Haidar), Mir Olim Bukhari's "Fathnomayi Sultani" (Sultan's Fathnama), Ahmad Mahdumi Donish's "Brief treatise on the history of the dynasty of the Mangits"[6], "Biographical situation of the emir of Bukhara" (written after 1885), "History of the Mangits" [7], Mirzo Abdulazim Sami Bostaniy (1838 /39-after 1914) from "History of Mangit Sultanate"[8], "History of Salimi" [9] by Mirza Salimbek (full name: Mirza Salimbek ibn Muhammad Rahim), "Useful History"[10] by Muhammad Ali Baljuvani. It was also used as an important source in studying the socio-political and economic situation of Eastern Bukhara provinces, including Surkhan oasis provinces, as well as the history of railways connecting the region with other places.

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